

**THE OBJECTIVES OF TEACHING PROBABILITY THEORY AND
MATHEMATICAL STATISTICS AND THE PRACTICE OF
ESTABLISHING AN INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTION IN THE
TEACHING OF THIS DISCIPLINE AND ITS APPLICATION IN
PRACTICE**

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Annotation: The applied significance of probability theory is that it can be considered as a theory of mathematical modeling of statistical laws of nature, which represent an idealized description of stable effects of averaging of very random phenomena. One of these patterns is the probability of an event.

Keywords: various definitions, skills and competencies, planning, problem

The probability of an event is its objective property, measured by frequency. An event has a certain probability if and only if, in repeated trials, the frequency of the event usually differs little from the probability with a sufficiently large repetition of the event. However, the question arises: what is considered "almost always coming", "big enough (small)" and, therefore, how objective is the definition of probability.

Special attention should be paid to determining the frequency of an event, its properties, the relationship between the frequency of an event and its probability (the definition of statistical probability), since it is on the axiom of the coincidence

of the properties of frequency and probability that the science of "Probability Theory" is built. In addition, the interrelation of various definitions of probability (classical, geometric, statistical) should be shown, their advantages and disadvantages are considered.

It should be noted that modern schoolchildren get acquainted with the "Theory of Probability" already in the 8th grade, and this section of mathematics is given quite a lot of attention, as evidenced by the presence of the corresponding task in the USE tests. But, as the practice of the author's work as the head of the school circle shows, the time allocated to this section is clearly not enough to form a correct understanding of the probability of an event. Perhaps this is due to the obviously insufficient life experience of eighth graders. Therefore, it is very important at the initial stage of studying the subject "Probability Theory" at the university to achieve a meaningful understanding of the concept of "probability", which will be further developed and expanded in the study of theorems and laws.

After describing random events, actions with them, a transition can be made to their set-theoretic nature, which is reflected in the fact that probability is a non-negative, additive normalized function of sets. Because there is no such discipline as "Logic" in modern working curricula, certain attention should be paid to the issues of logic algebra and set theory.

When studying the disciplines of the probabilistic cycle, difficulties often arise due to the cumbersomeness of formulas and "bad numbers" when analyzing real phenomena, the need for a large amount of routine calculations. Often, when performing them, students lose the logic of reasoning, do not see the connection between the formulation of the problem and the result obtained. Also, in engineering practice, tasks often arise, the analytical solution of which is often practically unrealizable or requiring too much time and/or costs. Therefore, the skills of numerical solution and modeling are of particular importance in the

framework of a systematic approach to solving the problem.

Mathematical education begins with concrete practical experience, exercises and moves on to abstract concepts. Professional experience is formed in practice. In this sense, the "practical-professional orientation of training" is of particular importance in the study of probability theory and mathematical statistics.

In pedagogical research, the term "practical orientation of learning" is defined as "the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies in the use of mathematical apparatus in solving specific practical problems through the implementation of the relevant content and methodological communication of mathematical education."

There is a scope of variation:

$$R = x_{max} - x_{min}$$

A sequence of variants of equal distance (shirt sizes) is created. To do this, the interval in which all values are entered is divided into several equal partial intervals, then the middle of each interval is determined, and these values form a sequence of equal distance options.

There is a number of division intervals:

$$N = \begin{cases} \text{int}(\sqrt[3]{10n}), n < 100 \\ \text{int}(5 \lg n), n \geq 100 \end{cases}$$

There is an interval step:

$$h = \frac{R}{N}$$

There will be a coefficient of variation, i.e. a percentage of the average value of the dimensional scattering:

$$V = \frac{\sigma_T}{x_T} \cdot 100\%$$

When solving problematic practical and professional tasks, it is necessary to

pay attention to the following:

- know and memorize the basic concepts, definitions, properties and formulas of probability theory and mathematical statistics;

- be able to plan your activities to solve the problem and determine which mathematical concepts can solve the problem;

- understand the essence of the problem.

The above guidelines should be applied at all stages of solving problematic practical and professional tasks: understanding the essence of the problem and taking the necessary practical actions, planning, problem solving and research.

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